

Disease resistance

Resistance of rice breeding lines to bacterial blight (BB) and stem rot (SR)

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We screened 91 genotypes with short to medium durations for reaction to BB *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye (leaf blight and kresek phase) and SR *Sclerotium oryzae* Cattaneo during 1984 wet season.

Each entry was planted in two 5-m-long rows, at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with BB

suspension at 21 d after transplanting (DT) for kresek and at 45 DT for leaf blight and scored at 30 and 14 d after inoculation. For screening for SR resistance, entries were planted in an infected plot and disease incidence recorded at maturity.

The leaf blight and kresek phases differed. Only 10 lines showed resistance to the kresek stage, but 30 showed resistance to the leaf blight phase.

HAU1 18-104, HKR120, CR294-548, and DV85 had resistance to both kresek and leaf blight phases (see table). Only HKR120 showed resistance to both phases of BB and to SR. HAU118-104, HAU118-154, HAU118-726, HAU83-164, RP2151-21-1, and TKM6 showed resistance to two problems and moderate resistance to one. These lines (except TKM6 and DV85) also have desirable agronomic traits. □

Reaction of rice lines to SR, and the kresek and leaf blight phases of BB in the field at HAU, RRS, Haryana, India, 1984 wet season.

Entry	Parentage	Days to 50% heading	Reaction ^a to		
			Kresek	Leaf blight	Stem rot
HAU118-104	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	109	R	R	MR
HAU118-106	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	104	MS	R	R
HAU118-111	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	106	R	MR	MR
HAU118-154	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	106	MR	R	R
HAU118-187	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	107	MR	R	MR
HAU118-726	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	104	R	MR	R
HAU118-788	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	108	MR	R	MR
HKR120	Ptb 33/4* IR3403-267-1	111	R	R	R
HKR122	Ptb 33/4* IR3403-267-1	115	MR	R	MR
HAU83-38	SFCIII/Basmati 370	106	MS	R	MR
HAU83-164	SFCIII/Basmati 370	122	MR	R	R
HAU83-222	SFCIII/Basmati 370	119	MR	R	MR
RP2151-21-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	110	MR	R	R
RP2151-224-4	IET4141/CR98-7216	122	MR	MR	R
RP2151-173-1-8	IET4141/CR98-7216	110	MR	R	MR
IET4141	IR8/BJ143//IR22	112	MS	R	R
IR54	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071-88// IR2061-214-3-6	121	MR	R	MR
CR3 19-644	-	110	MR	R	MR
CR294-548	-	108	R	R	MS
Govind	IR20/IR24	86	MR	R	MR
IR9784-142-1-3	IR1632-93-2-2/IR5534	101	MS	R	MR
IR13420-6-3-3	IR2863-38-1/2* IR36	109	MR	R	MR
TKM6	-	115	MR	R	R
DV85	-	92	R	R	S

^aR = resistant (score of 3 or lower), MR = moderately resistant (5), MS = moderately susceptible (7), and S = susceptible.

Field reaction of IR varieties to rice tungro (RTV)-associated viruses

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IR varieties planted in monthly planting trials in the experimental field at Maros and in the RTV nursery at Lanrang substation, South Sulawesi, were used to assess incidence of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) Aug-Oct 1986. Leaf samples were collected from 10 plants of each variety at 30 and at 45 d after transplanting (DT) and indexed by latex test.

RTBV and RTSV incidence varied with month of planting (Table 1).

Regardless of variety, virus incidence was higher in plots planted the last wk

Table 1. RTBV and RTSV incidence at 45 DT in 10 varieties planted on 1 Aug, 30 Aug, and 1 Oct, 1986, Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Planting date	Variety	Plants ^a (%) with	
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV
1 Aug 1986	IR26	0	10
	IR30	0	30
	IR42	30	0
	IR54	10	20
	IR58	0	0
	IR60	0	0
	IR62	0	0
	IR64	0	0
	TN1	70	0
	30 Aug	IR26	10
IR30		20	40
IR42		70	0
IR54		70	0
IR58		20	0
IR60		10	0
IR62		10	0
IR64		20	0
TN1		100	0
1 Oct		IR26	0
	IR30	30	10
	IR42	80	10
	IR54	30	10
	IR5	80	10
	IR6	00	0
	IR62	0	0
	IR64	10	10
	TN1	100	0

^aNo variety showed RTSV infection only.

of Aug. IR58, IR60, IR62, and IR64 had low or no RTBV + RTSV infection.

In the Lanrang RTV nursery, RTV incidence was high even at 30 DT (Table 2). IR50, IR52, IR54, IR58, and IR60 had high infection with RTBV + RTSV.

These results indicate that GLH-resistant varieties IR50, IR52, IR54, IR56, IR58, IR60, IR62, and IR64 can be attacked by RTV in South Sulawesi. Moderately resistant IR20 and IR26 were infected with RTBV only. □

Table 2. RTV incidence based on symptoms, and RTBV and RTSV incidence based on the latex test at 30 DT in 14 varieties. Lanrang, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, 1986.

Variety	RTV incidence (%)	Plant ^a (%) with	
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV
IR20	20	0	30
IR26	30	0	40
IR30	25	10	10
IR36	60	40	0
IR40	40	40	10
IR42	65	40	0
IR50	50	50	0
IR52	45	30	20
IR54	45	30	20
IR56	25	10	20
IR58	30	30	10
IR60	30	40	0
Kelara	5	0	10
TN1	85	70	0

^aNo variety showed RTSV infection only.

Reaction of International Rice Bacterial Blight Nursery (IRBBN) cultures to an Aduthurai, India, bacterial blight (BB) pathotype

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In Sep 1987 we screened IRBBN cultures against a pathotype of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* we had isolated. The Aduthurai pathotype drew reactions different from those to other Indian isolates (Table 1).

Plants were inoculated by clipping leaf tips with scissors dipped in

Table 1. Reaction of rice varieties to local BB isolates in India.

Isolate origin	Reaction of variety						
	IR20	TKM6	Cas 209	Kogyoku	DV85	IET4141	BJ1
Aduthurai	S	S	S	S	R	R	R
Cuttack	R	R	R	R	–	S	S
Hyderabad	R	R					
Haryana	R	R					
Pantnagar	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Delhi	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Punjab			R	R			
Pusa	R	R				S	
Maruteru (Andhra)						S	
Dholi (Assam)						S	
Kajat (Madhya Pradesh)						S	

Table 2. Reaction of rice varieties to the Aduthurai BB pathotype. Aduthurai, India, Sep 1987.

Culture	Parentage	Origin	Disease score ^a
RP2151-173-1-8	IET4141/CR98-7216	India	3
RP2151-40-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	India	3
Kachamota	–	Bangladesh	3
DV85	–	Bangladesh	3
RP2151-21-22	IET4141/CR98-7216	India	5
AC19-1-1	–	Bangladesh	5
IR33380-60-1-2	IR52/IR13240-39-3// IR9224-117-2-3	IRRI	5
Kuntlam	Peta/DGWG	Indonesia	7
Nigeria 5	–	Sri Lanka	7
IR20	Peta 3/TN1/TKM6	IRRI	7
BR161-26-58	Chandina/IR425-1-1-3	Bangladesh	7
BR285-5-6-6	Biplab/Chandina	Bangladesh	7
Camor	–	Indonesia	7
C721313	C651042/Milyang 23//C682032	Taiwan	7
IR13146-45-2	BG90-2/IR34//IR46	IRRI	7
IR24632-145-2-2	IR5657-33-2/ IR4707-106-3-2//IR48	IRRI	7
IR29295-70-1-1	IR36/Mashuri	IRRI	7
IR29341-85-3-1	IR54/IR46	IRRI	7
IR33356-22-3-1	IR52/IR48//IRS2	IRRI	7
IR33360-5-3-2	IR52/IR5657-33-2// IR9224-117-2-3-3	IRRI	7
Koiadigha	–	Bangladesh	7
Nancay P.A.	–	Argentina	7
RTN90-4	SML 81-B-25/R68	India	7
IR1545-339-2-2	IR24/DZ192	IRRI	9
IR8	Peta/DGWG	IRRI	9
BR315-12-1-4	IR5 (J)/Biplab	Bangladesh	9
BR319-1-HR 28	IR5 (D) Biplab	Bangladesh	9
B40750-PN-13-1	E2484 B/2-PN-29-2/IR36	Indonesia	9
C712311	C681065/TCS254	Taiwan	9
C731051	C701040/C701027	Taiwan	9
C731067	C681030/IR13429-57-1	Taiwan	9
IRAT109	IRAT13/IRAT10	Ivory Coast	9
IR11288-8-8-445	IR36/Leb Mue Nahng III	IRRI/Thailand	9
IR33355-39-1-1	IR52/IR46/IR6115-1-1-1	IRRI	9
IR5853-213-6-1	Nam Sagui 19/ IR2071-88//IR2061-214-3-6	IRRI	9
Kalimekri-77-5	–	Japan	9
Kogyoku	Shirosenbon/Shobei	Bangladesh	9
RP1575-143-823-1	TNI/Luangu	India	9
UPR79-80	–	India	9
TN1	DGWG/Tsai-Yuan-Chan	Taiwan	9

^aBy SES.